

Raktbeej: A Deeper Insight into an Advanced Framework for Blockchain-Based Royalty Distribution in Academic Publishing and Citations

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Abstract—Research often lacks an incentive mechanism, and traditional Academic Publishing lacks transparent and equitable mechanisms to reward researchers. This paper introduces the platform “Raktbeej”, a blockchain-based system inspired by retroactive public goods funding, which allows authors to define royalty distribution percentages for cited works. Using smart contracts, Raktbeej automates the distribution of royalties to cited authors whenever a donation is made to an author. The potential of the platform to transform academic publishing for the better is evaluated.

Index Terms—Blockchain, Academic Publishing, Decentralized Science, Smart Contracts, Citations, Ethereum, Retroactive Public Goods Funding

I. INTRODUCTION

Research is the compass of humanity which has shaped the modern world, and yet there are not enough incentives to pursue research. Traditional models favor publishers by hiding journals behind paywalls and imposing article processing fees, while authors and cited authors receive little to no direct monetary benefit. Blockchain technology offers a decentralized solution to these challenges while bypassing currency conversion fees, sanctions, and other bureaucratic hurdles [3]–[6]. Raktbeej empowers authors to allocate royalty percentages to cited works. When a reader, institution, or blockchain donates

funds, smart contracts automatically distribute royalties based on predefined splits—ensuring transparency, immutability, and fairness.

Raktbeej draws inspiration from retroactive public goods funding, a concept familiarized by Optimism [1], where projects that have already delivered value are rewarded post-impact. In academia, this translates to compensating authors for high-value papers that have proven impactful through citations or breakthroughs.

II. BACKGROUND

Retroactive public goods funding rewards contributions after proving their worth [1], inspiring Raktbeej’s approach to valuing papers post-upload. Decentralized science (DeSci) leverages blockchain to democratize funding, review, and access, challenging centralized publishing. Raktbeej uses IPFS [2] for storage and blockchain for royalties, with off-chain peer review and community feedback enhancing its DeSci alignment.

III. FRAMEWORK

Raktbeej integrates blockchain, IPFS, and DeSci principles to manage royalties retroactively.

A. Author Registration

Authors register by creating accounts and adding wallet addresses to the platform.

B. Paper Upload and Royalty Setting

Flow Overview: To understand the mechanics of uploading and storing a paper on the blockchain, Fig. 1 illustrates the workflow.

Fig. 1. Flow of uploading and storing paper using IPFS and blockchain. Arrows labeled [(1)–(4)] indicate the flow.

In Fig. 1, the author uploads a PDF, enters title, co-author and cited author wallet addresses, and defines royalty percentages. Metadata is stored in Neon DB while the PDF is stored in IPFS via Pinata; the resulting IPFS hash is linked back in the database.

C. Donation and Distribution

Donations in cryptocurrency are logged on the blockchain. Smart contracts split funds between the author’s and cited authors’ wallets per the royalty percentage. Fig. 2 illustrates this flow.

Fig. 2. Flow of donated money using Solidity smart contract. Arrows labeled [(1)–(4)] indicate the flow.

The donor specifies an amount via the front-end [flow (1)]. Neon DB fetches associated wallets [flow (2)] which are sent to the Solidity contract [flow (3)] triggering the distribution [flow (4)].

D. Database Design

Raktbeej employs a relational schema in Neon DB to manage off-chain data for users, papers, and royalties.

Fig. 3. Database design using Neon DB.

Core tables:

- **users:** stores author info, wallets, and donation totals.
- **papers:** contains paper metadata and IPFS links.
- **royaltysplits:** defines cited authors’ wallets and split percentages.

E. Integrating Webhooks

Webhooks enable event-driven backend automation—triggering royalty splits and database updates when authors register or upload papers.

F. Smart Contract

```
// SPDX-License-Identifier: MIT
pragma solidity ^0.8.19;

contract OpenDonationSplitter {
    /**
     * @notice Split the sent ETH among recipients based on their percentage shares.
     * @param recipients Array of recipient addresses
     * @param percentages Array of corresponding percentages (in basis points: 10000 = 100%)
     */
    function donateAndSplit(
        address[] calldata recipients,
        uint256[] calldata percentages
    ) external payable {
        uint256 totalAmount = msg.value;
        uint256 totalPercentage = 0;

        require(recipients.length == percentages.length, "Mismatched array lengths");
        require(totalAmount > 0, "Must send ETH");

        // Sum percentages and validate
        for (uint256 i = 0; i < percentages.length; i++) {
            totalPercentage += percentages[i];
        }
        require(totalPercentage == 10000, "Total percentages must equal 100 (100%)");

        // Distribute ETH
        for (uint256 i = 0; i < recipients.length; i++) {
            uint256 amount = (totalAmount * percentages[i]) / 10000;
            (bool success, ) = payable(recipients[i]).call{value: amount}("");
            require(success, "Transfer failed");
        }
    }
}
```

Fig. 4. Solidity smart contract implementing royalty split logic.

Explanation: The `OpenDonationSplitter` contract allows users to send ETH donations that are automatically divided among multiple recipients. Key points:

- `donateAndSplit()` is payable and validates equal array lengths and 100 % total share.
- Each author receives ETH proportional to their share.
- Uses `call()` for safe transfers and reverts on failure.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND CURRENT OUTCOMES

Fig. 5. Landing page.

Fig. 6. Sign-in page.

Fig. 7. Upload page where author chooses file and enters details.

Fig. 8. Author enters royalty split percentages and wallet addresses.

Fig. 9. Preview of selected file before upload.

Fig. 12. Explore page showing all uploaded papers.

Fig. 10. Upload success notification after storing on IPFS & Neon DB.

Fig. 13. User view of a paper with donation option.

Fig. 11. Post-upload preview for the author.

Fig. 14. Testing the deployed smart contract on Remix IDE.

Fig. 15. Donor interface showing donation input in ETH/USDT.

Fig. 16. MetaMask confirmation window before sending the donation.

Fig. 19. The wallet pop-up requesting to confirm the transaction.

Fig. 17. Once the amount is entered and the Donate button is clicked, the API fetches the wallet addresses and their respective royalty split percentage associated with that particular paper.

Fig. 18. After the wallet addresses and royalty split percentages are fetched, the application sends request to donor's wallet to confirm the transaction.

Fig. 20. Once the transaction request is approved, the transaction begins and the smart contract is triggered and the money is dripped to all the authors of that paper.

Fig. 21. After the transaction completes successfully, the donor sees donation successful dialog.

Flow of how the platform works:

- Once the user enters our platform, they will be on the landing page [Fig. 5].
- Authors need to sign-in/sign-up to upload papers and Clerk provides a seamless auth service [Fig. 6].
- The author will need to upload the document in PDF formatted file and enter the details like *Document Title, Main Topic/Keywords* [Fig. 7.]. And the author can add co-authors' and/or cited authors' wallet addresses and the royalty splits[Fig. 8.].
- The Author gets to see the preview of the chosen document before actually uploading it on the platform [Fig. 9.].
- Author gets a success notification once the file and other metadata was stored successfully in the platform's database [Fig. 10.] and a file preview again after uploading it successfully [Fig. 11.].
- Users/Viewers can enter into our platform directly without requiring any sign-up and can view the /papers page and explore all the papers on this platform [Fig. 12.].
- By clicking on a specific paper, they enter a detailed view of the paper with a dialog box on the right which contains all the metadata details of the paper and get option to donate and support the author [Fig. 13.].
- If a donor wants to donate, they can just enter the amount in the given dialog box and click on *Donate Now* button and the API fetches the wallet addresses and their respective royalty split percentage associated with that particular paper [Fig. 17] and is sent to the smart contract where the *OpenDonationSplitter* function [Fig. 4] is triggered and the transaction begins.
- Once all the data is fetched by the API and the smart

contract triggers, the donor will be asked to confirm the requested transaction as shown in [Fig. 18.] and [Fig. 19.].

- After confirming, the author gets the transaction hash and the *waiting for confirmation..* text [Fig. 20.].
- Once the transaction is completely successful and the receiver receives the money, the donor gets a *Donation successful* notification [Fig. 21.].
- **Registering:** Using Clerk's authentication service, users are able to register to our platform easily.
- **Paper upload:** Authors can upload papers seamlessly with just a button click and the IPFS [2] hashed(CID) Pinata URL is stored in the Neon DB properly which keeps retrieval of the paper consistent and safe.
- **Royalty split function:** The smart contract is being triggered and the amount is split exactly according to the specified split percentage and dripped correctly and the transactions are successful.

V. POTENTIAL BENEFITS

Raktbeej offers several advantages:

- **Retroactive Filtering:** Funding reflects impact, naturally filtering out low-value papers without gatekeeping.
- **Open Access:** Uploads without pre-review democratize publishing, aligning with DeSci.
- **Credible Review:** Requiring reviewers to have uploaded papers ensures informed feedback.
- **Community Engagement:** Feedback fosters collaboration and iterative improvement.
- **Fairness:** Cited authors receive royalties, incentivizing high-quality citations.

These features could create an inclusive, impact-driven publishing model.

VI. CHALLENGES

Despite its potential, the Raktbeej platform faces several challenges:

- **Wallet Accuracy:** Manual input of cited authors' wallet addresses risk causing errors and misdirect the funds.
- **Adoption:** Getting researchers and the layman familiar with cryptocurrency and gaining mass adoption is one of the biggest challenges.
- **Limited Domain:** The retroactive approach limits the domain in which research can be done because some fields like nuclear fission require substantial amounts of donation and infrastructure to perform research.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

- **Peer review system:** An off-chain review system which is carried out by registered users who have uploaded at least one paper (as proof of work) on this platform ensuring reviewer credibility. The reviews are submitted on the same platform which provides authors feedback for optional revisions in their work and the updated paper can be re-uploaded to IPFS [2].
- **Monetary support for researchers:** Users will be able to support their favorite researcher by donating a fixed

amount of money as recurring monthly donations or a one-time donation. This helps and motivates the researcher to do more work.

- **Venture Capital ecosystem for novel research:** As research alone does not become an innovation, integrating a network of venture capital firms, accelerators and other supporting structures which would indeed help in turning a groundbreaking novel research into real-world impact-driven viable venture.
- **Groups for research:** Adding a collaborative feature where different researchers can work together in a collaborative manner on a specific research which can help bring in the knowledge from different fields and combine them together for a new innovation or divide the work and make the research easy on an individual researcher.
- **Integrating Emerging Ethereum Standards(ERC-7683)** To enhance scalability and support interoperability of different chains and cross-chain transactions the platform could adopt to ERC-7683 [?] . This scales the users to global blockchain users and there will be no chain barriers to use our platform. This also could eventually reduce gas fee and offers a smoother multi-recipient flow of money which boosts our royalty split system.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Raktbeej, inspired by retroactive public goods funding and embedded in decentralised science, offers a blockchain-based platform for royalties, peer review, and feedback. Authors upload papers to IPFS [2], specifying cited authors' wallet addresses and royalty percentages, with smart contracts automating distribution. Off-chain peer review by platform authors and community feedback enhance quality, while retroactive funding filters low-value works. Challenges like review consistency and scalability persist, but Raktbeej's potential to democratise publishing is significant. Future work could explore reviewer reputation systems, feedback curation, and pilots within DeSci communities to refine and validate the approach.

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